

DETERMINANTS OF FOREIGN DIRECT INVESTMENT IN NIGERIA

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Abstract

This paper evaluates the determinants of foreign direct investment in Nigeria within a multivariate framework from 1980-2020. The Central Bank of Nigeria statistical bulletin (various issues), the National Bureau of Statistics and the World Bank's world development indicators were the source of the information utilized in this article. The autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) bounds test is employed in establishing the long-run relationship among the variables. The results reveal that there is a long-run relationship between the macroeconomic variables used in this research. Precisely, the result shows that real gross domestic product has a positive and significant impact on foreign direct investment both in the short run and long; exchange rate and degree of trade openness have a positive and significant influence on foreign direct investment in the long run; inflation rate has a negative and significant effect on foreign direct investment in the long run. Hence, it was recommended that government should ensure the economic atmosphere is conducive for foreign investors; provide the needed infrastructure and amenities to boost economic growth; provide an adequate level of security in the country; formulate policies to ensure stable exchange rates; adopt uniform tax policies; adopt an economic policy of privatization, liberalization and globalization.

Keywords: Foreign Direct Investment, Real Gross Domestic Product, Exchange Rate, Inflation Rate, Degree of Trade Openness.

JEL Classification Codes: F20, F21, F31

1. Introduction

Most developing and emerging economies are characterized by inadequate funds, capital, or finance at the macroeconomic level. This is not enough for them to carry out numerous investment and productive activities. Thus, to finance their investment initiatives, these countries look for domestic or international capital, either through direct investment or portfolio investment, which is an alternative to direct debits. Trade, political as well as economic cooperation among nations is a key step in establishing multinational or foreign corporations in any country and providing it with the attributes and facilities to carry out its operations. In addition, the government at all levels can also play a crucial part in the legislation and formulation of laws that relate to foreign investment; be it direct or portfolio, which might assist in creating competition in the market.

According to Hill (2005), FDI occurs when a company directly invests in facilities or services to create or sell goods in a foreign country and it is more often than not undertaken by Multinational corporations (MNCs) or Multinational enterprises. MNCs or MNEs are companies that have their businesses or interest spread over several countries, although controlled by a central headquarter,(Stoner, Freeman & Gilbert2007).Recently, it is observed that FDI in most countries is a result of many factors such as exports, integration into the international market, financial development, and technological advancement. Agiomirgianakis, Asteriou & Papathoma (2003) thought that most corporations are seeking to participate in FDI to gain some benefits such as market preferences, infrastructure, monopoly reduction, tax, and customs exemption. The growth and advancement of FDI have to support domestic savings by formulating laws and regulations to support its operations. Okonkwo, Egbunke & Udeh (2015) believed that FDI is deemed to have filled up the gaps in technology, entrepreneurship, and management, due to spill overs and other externalities. Additionally, FDI is viewed as a way to bridge the gap between industrialized and undeveloped nations, where both domestic and foreign capital contributes to filling any shortages (Montiel & Reinhart 1999).

FDI plays a part in economic growth and development by employing human resources, financial resources, administrative expertise, and marketing which indicates an increase in employment rates at the macroeconomic level. Many academics have suggested that FDI represents a considerable economic stimulus. It seems to be the most significant aspect of capital inflows, entailing the transfer of resources such as money, technology, management and marketing know-how (Ajudua & Devis, 2015). To encourage cross-border investments, aimed at economic growth and development, FDI is one of the key features of today's economic goals of nations (Ajudua & Bakare-Aremu, 2018).Furthermore, it might play a role in strengthening financial institutions, improving stock prices, and increasing trading volume as well as the market value in the equity market, which in addition, is an attraction for private investors and a key function in the economies of any nation-state. A good number of African nations, Nigeria inclusive, have had various reformations in their investment laws, the financial system as well as economic policies, to make a conducive environment available for FDI, (OECD Development Centre & AfDB 2006). For a variety of reasons such as the exchange of technological and scientific research partnerships, the Sub-Saharan Africa region must rely substantially on FDI (Asiedu 2001). The occurrence of various financial crises at different times has shown that a diversified venture is preferred to counterbalance any risks or potential losses between the economies of various countries, (Haile & Assefa, 2006). Most African developing economies recently have not been able to draw FDI inflows like their Asian counterparts. In 2017, a total FDI inflow of \$42USD billion came into Africa, which is a 21% drop from the 2016 FDI inflows. This was ascribed to the continuous decline in crude oil prices as well as unfavourable circumstances in these host African countries' macroeconomic variables (UNCTAD, 2018).Despite this, over the previous decades, FDI inflows have contributed about 20% of the growth in fixed capital formation in Africa, although it remains in the favour of the oil-rich nations which comprise 75% of FDI inflows (AfDB, OECE, UNDP& UNECA. (2011) 2011). As of 2020, Nigeria was the major producer and exporter of

crude oil in Africa and the seventh in the world; it exported about USD 30 billion worth of crude oil, approximately 4.68% of the global total. This is a significant factor in why the nation has drawn a lot of FDI inflows throughout time. According to a UNCTAD analysis from 2006, Nigeria received almost 70% of the FDI that entered the ECOWAS area.

Fig 1: FDI Inflow into Nigeria and FDI percentage of Nigeria's GDP from 1970 to 2021

Source: World Bank; <https://www.macrotrends.net/countries/NGA/nigeria/foreign-direct-investment>

Figure 1 above reveals that in 1970, FDI inflow in Nigeria was \$205 Million, after wards it raised to \$470 million in 1975. This was credited to the government's unwavering commitment to encouraging private sector participation in the oil and gas sector. Also, in 1989, the Nigeria National Petroleum Corporation (NNPC) cut down its picket in shell Nigeria as well as other oil companies from 80% to 60%, this was valued at more than \$ 1 billion, subsequently, FDI inflow into Nigeria has never fallen less than \$1 billion per year which too had an affirmative effect. Nigeria as a principal target of FDI inflows in Africa during the 1970 and the mid-1990s accounted for more than 30% of all FDI inflows to the continent, this was due to its enormous crude oil production and reserves. Though, from 2007 to 2009 its prominent position in attracting FDI began to deteriorate as a result of the rise of FDI inflow into other crude oil-rich nations; for instance, Sudan and Angola. The increased activities of FDI in other key African nations like Egypt, the Republic of Congo, and South Africa, which were successful in luring FDI in various sectors of their economies, are another factor contributing to Nigeria's drop in FDI attraction. Nevertheless, Nigeria continues to be the biggest recipient of FDI within the ECOWAS, accounting for more than 70% of regional inflows as early as 2001. In the 1970s, it received around half of the FDI that entered ECOWAS. As a result, foreign direct investment (FDI) in the Nigerian economy contributes significantly to the country's capital accumulation. In 2009, FDI accounted for 30.9 per cent of the average annual Gross Fixed Capital Formation (GFCF), compared to 18.7 per cent on average for the rest of Africa and 9.3per cent for

developing economies worldwide. Among 141 economies worldwide, the country is ranked 56 in 2009 by the inward FDI performance indicator and inward FDI potential index (UNCTAD 2010). Thus, the objective of this treatise is to identify and ascertain the factors that have an impact on foreign investment in the Nigerian economy.

Pragmatic proof of foreign direct investment revealed varied outcomes or contradictory findings (Adeleke, Olowe&Fasesin, 2014; Ojong, Arikpo&Ogar, 2015; Achugamonu, Ailemen, Taiwo& Okorie, 2016, Ndubuisi, 2017). This might be credited to data sources and coverage as well as the type of econometric procedure utilized. This study was necessary because of these inconsistencies, which call for more research on the factors that influence foreign direct investment in Nigeria. This paper is set up and arranged as follows: theoretical foundation: which includes the foreign direct investment in Nigeria and literature review, research methodology: which includes the variables employed in the model, model specification as well as hypotheses, empirical results, and discussion. Finally, the study has its conclusion and recommendations.

2. Theoretical Literature

One of the earliest theoretical approaches to understanding foreign direct investment is the neoclassical growth theory. Solow (1956) tried to explain a growth model into an uncomplicated production function and looked at significant macroeconomic variables that may perhaps make steady growth rates available. Conversely, inside the endogenous growth theory, FDI flows can directly or indirectly cause economic growth in a country (Enu, Havi & Attah-Obeng, 2013).

One of the major tenets of the economic growth theory is that foreign direct investment and economic growth are significantly a favourability correlated, which strengthens efficiency and productivity, enhances technology, and encourages competitive benefits in markets. In addition, the neoclassical growth theories imply that one key means to raise funds to improve productivity is foreign direct investment. This indicates that for there to be adequate economic growth in any nation, it requires the flow of both domestic and foreign capital into investments and productive activities. Furthermore, the endogenous growth theories propose that optimal utilization of resources in terms of knowledge, innovation, creativity, and technology can lead to long-term economic growth and that foreign investment can speed up this process (Adams, 2009). From these various macroeconomic theories discussed; we can observe that presently, foreign direct investment in the federal republic of Nigeria is a major economic challenge in how to make up for the plunge in crude oil prices and rising level of insecurity. This signifies that the nation has got to diversify as well as increase its exports through mechanized agriculture, enhanced manufactured goods, and improved security, especially in the northeast and southeast regions to attract foreign investors and bring in foreign capital into the Nigerian economy. In recent times, the federal government of Nigeria has focused on its indigenization policy and this is likely to reduce foreign remittances abroad and therefore support inward investments utilizing foreign direct investment for economic growth. Furthermore, it was observed that infrastructural development plays a vital part not only to support the nation's

economy; but also, in the successful operations of indigenous companies to perform and compete favourably with foreign companies via product expansion as well as efficient customer services. This will reduce costs and assist foreign investors to carry out their operations, thus, increasing the rate of return on their investments. What is more, the easy access to natural resources and skilled labour force encourages the influx of foreign direct investment in addition to capital resources in numerous manufacturing sectors in the country.

2.1 Empirical Literature

Quite several types of research have highlighted the significance of attracting foreign direct investment (FDI) to developing economies as well as trade and industrial openness as macroeconomic policies that developing economies ought to engage in (Asiedu 2003; Akinkugbe 2003). Akinlo (2004) used data from 1970 to 2001 and the error correlation model to determine that FDI had little effect on Nigeria's economic growth. Oyejide (2005) used a conceptual framework for analyzing the macroeconomic impact of volatile capital flows in the Nigerian economy. He concluded that capital flows have their pros and cons, but this relies on the initial situation of the developing economy under consideration. In the view of Aseiedu (2006), exchange rate and low inflation rate influence FDI in an economy. Furthermore, he asserted that a country with sufficient basic amenities and infrastructures, a stable political sphere, an adequate employment rate, a conducive business environment, and is free from corruption can attract FDI inflow. His avowal was supported by Ayanwale (2007) who opined that infrastructure development and stable macroeconomic policy induce FDI. Conversely, Ogbulu & Paul (2009) sees inflation rate, real official exchange rate, market size, and political risk factors as variables that significantly influence FDI inflows to Nigeria. From a different viewpoint, Isam (2010) identified the primary variables that frequently impact the investment decisions of foreigners as being the availability of infrastructure, acceptable security, and strong economic performance.

To investigate the effect and relationship between FDI and economic growth in Nigeria, Oyatoye, Arogundade, Adebisi, & Oluwakayode (2011) utilized secondary data from 1987 to 2006. They established a link favourable between FDI and Nigeria's economic growth. Uwubamwen & Ajao (2012) used the co-integration technique to study the impact of FDI in Nigeria from 1970 to 2009. They found out that the key variables influencing FDI influx into the country were the consumer price index, exchange rate, trade openness, and interest rate. Mukolu, Otalú, & Awosusi (2013) investigated how FDI affected Nigeria by employing the error correction model (ECM). Their findings suggested that FDI has significant long-term and short-term effects on the expansion of Nigeria's economy. Saibu & Akinbobola (2014) used the Vector Error Correction Modeling (VECM) technique to examine the link between FDI, globalization, and economic growth in selected Sub-Saharan African nations. They found that in Sub-Saharan African countries, trade liberalization and the process of economic growth had nothing in common. Time-series data and the Pearson Correlation coefficient were used by Adigwe, Ezeagba, & Francis (2015) to analyze the link between FDI, exchange rate, and GDP in Nigeria. Their findings indicated a substantial link between FDI, exchange rate, and GDP, indicating that FDI and exchange rate significantly affect Nigeria's economic growth. Adeyeye, Akinuli, & Ayodele (2016) investigated the relationship between inflation, security spending,

and FDI influx in Nigeria from 1985 to 2015 using the Error Correction Model method. According to their research, FDI is inversely associated with spending on security and inflation. However, in the long run, Nigeria's FDI inflow and defence spending are closely related. Enisan (2017) used the Markov-regime switching model (MSMs) to examine the factors that influenced foreign direct investment in Nigeria between 1970 and 2012. According to his research, GDP growth, macroeconomic instability, financial development, exchange rate, inflation, and discount rate are the primary drivers of FDI. Aderemi, Olayemi, Ebere, & Adeniran (2018) used the Granger causality and dynamic Ordinary Least Square to look into the relationship between security expenditure and FDI inflows in Nigeria from 1994 to 2016. Their research showed a positive relationship between internal security expenditures and FDI inflows in Nigeria as well as a bidirectional causal relationship between defence spending and FDI inflows in the nation. Abiola (2019) examined the factors influencing FDI inflows into the Nigerian economy using the structural vector auto regression method and discovered that inflation rate and exchange rate were the most important factors that determine FDI inflow into the country. Aderemi, Ganiyu, Sokunbi, & Bako (2020) used an empirical investigation to appraise the determinants of FDI inflows in Nigeria and found out that past FDI inflow, market size, exchange rate, and growth rate had a positive and significant influence on driving FDI inflows into the country. Orji, Nwagu, Ogbuabor, & Anthony-Orji (2021) assessed the impact of FDI on economic growth in Nigeria using the ARDL approach. Their findings showed that, over the studied time, FDI had a favourable and significant link with economic growth in Nigeria.

3. Methodology

The quantitative approach was used in this study as an empirical methodology. Data were gathered by relying on annual reports from the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) statistical bulletin and the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) for a period spanning forty-one years, 1980 to 2020.

3.1 Variables and Models Specification

Several researchers converse on the determinants of FDI in Nigeria such as Enisan (2017), Abiola (2019), & Aderemi et al (2020). This article selected four variables as independent variables connected to the model as follows: Real Gross Domestic Product (RGDP), Exchange Rate (EXCR), Inflation Rate (INF), Degree of Trade Openness (DTO), and Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) as the dependent variable for the model. The data for these variables were gotten from the Central Bank of Nigeria statistical bulletin (various issues), National Bureau of Statistics, and World Bank Economic Indicators

The model is presented thus:

$$FDI = f(RGDP, EXCR, INF, DTO) \quad 1$$

When expressed linearly becomes

$$FDI_{it} = \varphi_0 + \varphi_1 RGDP_{it} + \varphi_2 EXCR_{it} + \varphi_3 INF_{it} + \varphi_4 DTO_{it} + \mu_{it} \quad 2$$

Where $\varphi_0 - \varphi_4$ are the parameter estimates and μ_{it} is the error term. Apriori expectation for the model is as follows: $\varphi_1 > 0$, $\varphi_2 > 0$, $\varphi_3 < 0$, $\varphi_4 > 0$.

The hypothesis of the Model

H_0 : There is no statistically significant relationship between each independent variable (RGDP, EXCR, INF, and DTO) and Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) in Nigeria

4. Empirical Result and Discussion

4.1 Descriptive Statistics Analysis Discussion

Table 1 below provides a descriptive analysis of the macroeconomic variables considered in this study.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics Analysis

	FDI	RGDP	EXCR	INF	DTO
Mean	2.75E+09	38991.39	112.0037	18.36798	0.319375
Median	1.88E+09	31874.99	119.7685	12.36896	0.332337
Maximum	8.84E+09	71387.83	358.8108	72.80000	0.555734
Minimum	1.93E+08	16997.52	0.893750	5.386104	0.075976
Std. Dev.	2.60E+09	19710.15	100.1918	16.56303	0.104640
Skewness	1.040331	0.491380	0.781212	1.891117	-0.287685
Kurtosis	2.856225	1.632781	2.868888	5.617003	2.953664
Jarque-Bera	6.524744	4.252657	3.687536	31.73100	0.499798
Probability	0.038297	0.119274	0.158220	0.000000	0.778879
Sum	9.90E+10	1403690.	4032.132	661.2471	11.49752
Sum Sq. Dev.	2.36E+20	1.36E+10	351343.6	9601.685	0.383237
Observations	41	41	41	41	41

Source: Author's Computation 2022 based on E-views

The descriptive statistics for each of the variables included in the model from 1980 to 2020 are shown in Table 1 above. From table 1, it is noticed that RGDP's standard deviation is larger than that of other economic variables. This shows that when compared to other indicators, RGDP is more erratic and volatile. The skewness test, which assesses the asymmetry of the distribution of the series, shows that all economic variables, with the exception of DTO, have positive skewed values. This signifies that FDI, RGDP, EXCR, and INF are skewed to the right and that their right tails are longer, while DTO is negatively skewed to the left and has a long-left tail. The Kurtosis, which gauges how peaky or flat the series' distribution is, reveals that shows that since INF's kurtosis statistics are larger than 3, it are very leptokurtic. Nevertheless, the distribution of FDI, RGDP, EXCR, and DTO are highly platy kurtic relative to the normal.

4.2 Unit Root Test

This study used the well-known unit root test to check if each of these variables had a unit root (non-stationary) or not (stationary series) in order to examine their time-series properties. Table 2 below displays the results of the unit root test.

Table 2: Unit Root Test Result

Variables	ADF – statistics	Critical values		Order of Integration
LFDI	-6.910763	1% level	-3.653730	I(1)
		5% level	-2.957110	
		10% level	-2.617434	
LRGDP	-3.619575	1% level	-3.639407	I(1)
		5% level	-2.951125	
		10% level	-2.614300	
LEXCR	-3.444964	1% level	-3.632900	I(0)
		5% level	-2.948404	
		10% level	-2.612874	
LINF	-5.002456	1% level	-3.639407	I(1)
		5% level	-2.951125	
		10% level	-2.614300	
LDTO	-3.360410	1% level	-3.632900	I(0)
		5% level	-2.948404	
		10% level	-2.612874	

Source: Author’s Computation 2022 based on E-views

Table 2 shows the results of the ADF test, which showed that EXCR and DTO were stationary at levels and did not have unit roots. All three variables, FDI, RGDP, and INF, had unit roots; hence they were all differenced once to become integrated. As a result, the variables included in the study had a combination of I (0) and I(1) stationarity properties, therefore, the utilization of the ARDL bounds testing technique for co-integration would be apt.

Table 3: VAR Lag Order Selection Criteria

Lag	LogL	LR	FPE	AIC	SC	HQ
0	-413.208	NA	18010.822	23.10303	23.38057	23.21351
1	-252.885	137.14319	12141.011	15.08218	17.42500	15.71551
2	-202.472	47.43271*	4143.314*	14.15233*	17.03011*	15.32848*

*Indicate lag order selected by the criterion (each at 5% level)

Source: Author’s Computation based on E-views

From table 3, the optimal lag length of the variables included in the ARDL model was selected based on the LR, FPE, AIC SC, and HQ, indicating an optimal lag length of two (2).

4.3 ARDL Bounds Co-integration Test

Table 4 below displays the results of the ARDL co-integration bound test. It reveals whether there is a long-run relationship between the variables.

Table 4: ARDL Bounds Co-integration Test

F-Bounds Test		Null Hypothesis: No levels of relationship		
Test Statistic	Value	Signif.	I(0)	I(1)
Asymptotic: n=1000				
F-statistic	9.936402	10%	2.45	3.52
K	4	5%	2.86	4.01
		2.5%	3.25	4.49
		1%	3.74	5.06

Source: Author’s computation 2022 based on E-views

Table 4 above illustrates that the calculated F-statistic is more than the upper and lower bound critical value at a 5% level of significance. As a result, the study rejects the null hypothesis that there is no co-integration, indicating a long-run relationship between FDI, RGDP, EXCR, INF, and DTO.

4.4. Long-Run and Short-Run Estimates

The long-run and short-run estimations for equation 1 were evaluated due to the long-run relationship between FDI, RGDP, EXCR, INF, and DTO. The findings are displayed in Table 5 below.

Table 5: Long-Run and Short-Run Estimates

Panel A: Long-run coefficients (dependent variable is FDI) for Model 1			
Regressors	Coefficient	T-statistic	P-value
Constant	-0.081071	-0.322548	0.7526
RGDP	24.97703	4.268783	0.0027
EXCR	1.380692	2.519756	0.0358
INF	-1.600364	-5.191918	0.0008
DTO	2.049684	3.245995	0.0118
Panel B: Short-run results (dependent variable Δ FDI)			
Regressors	Coefficient	T-statistic	P-value
Δ RGDP	8.855426	2.220429	0.0464
Δ EXCR	-0.651860	-0.651860	0.2917
Δ INF	-0.458613	-1.391876	0.1892
Δ DTO	-0.538177	-1.274510	0.2266
ECM _{t-1}	-0.750207	-3.191113	0.0078
R ² = 0.843866		Adjusted R ² = 0.596653	
F-statistic = 18.96379		Prob (F statistic) = 0.000106	

Source: Author’s computation 2022 based on E-views

Results for both the long and short runs are shown in Table 5. (Panel A and Panel B) demonstrate that, regardless of the time period, the RGDP coefficient is positive and

statistically significant. For instance, a unit increase in RGDP results in a 24.97703 unit increase in FDI in the long run and in the short-run, an increase of about 8.855426 units. These findings suggest that RGDP is essential for FDI attraction in Nigeria, both in the long run and short run. The increase in Nigeria's RGDP might be due to the increase in government expenditure, especially on capital projects like roads, trains, power, etc. Also, the increase in the country's RGDP might be attributed to the government's catalytic role through the formulation of policies and delivery of financing havens to promote the real sector to heights that can make the country an economic nucleus and a driver of Africa's economic resurgence. A large RGDP in Nigeria provides high-profit opportunities and thus, attracts higher FDI. This result is in line with the findings of Mawugnon & Qiang, (2011).

Additionally, the outcome demonstrates that the coefficient of EXCR is positive and statistically significant in the long run. For example, a unit rise in EXCR lead leads 1.380692 unit rise in FDI in the long run. This suggests that EXCR is crucial in attracting FDI in Nigeria in the long run. The rise in EXCR might be due to the fall in the global crude oil prices, FOREX inflows, and profit-taking from the redemption of the federal government of Nigeria's bonds, etc. When Nigeria's EXCR is high compared to other currencies, particularly the US dollars, it reduces its wages and production costs in comparison to its overseas competitors. All things being equal, it has improved location advantage or attractiveness as a location for getting FDI. This finding is supported by the result of Vincent, Inaya & Proso (2017).

INF from the result reveals that it is negative and statistically significant in the long run. A unit increase in INF, for example result to approximately a 1.600364 unit fall in FDI in the long run. This signifies that INF in the long run is vital in attracting FDI in Nigeria. The rise in INF might be attributed to an expansion of the money supply in the economy, a rise in public spending, civil unrest, an upsurge in the prices of petroleum products, higher taxes etc.

Nigeria's high INF creates uncertainty, makes exports more expensive, reduces international competitiveness, discourages FDI, and destroys the economy. Conversely, if INF is low in the Nigerian economy, it is an indication of economic stability and inevitably attracts FDI. This result is supported by the works of Abdul & Taskeen (2019).

DTO in the long run as shown by the result is positive and statistically significant. For example, a unit rise in DTO, in the long run, brings about a 2.049684 unit rise in FDI. This means that DTO is crucial in bringing FDI inflows to Nigeria in the long run. The rise in DTO might be a result of reforms in trade policy, the fight against corruption, political stability, exchange rate policies etc. A rise in Nigeria's DTO helps the transfer of technology, knowledge, and skill and influences the influx of FDI into the economy. This finding is supported by the result of Wiredu, Nketiah, & Adjei (2020).

In the short run, EXCR, INF and DTO were statistically insignificant as indicated by the result. The coefficient of the ECM_{t-1} as shown from the result is -0.750207 and it is statistically significant with a P-value of 0.0078. This suggests that the speed of adjustment between the short-run dynamics and the long-run equilibrium is 75.02% in absolute value. The coefficient of determination ($R^2 = 0.843866$) reveals that 84% of the overall variation in FDI is explained

by the variations in RGDP, EXCR, INF and DTO while 16% of the total variation in FDI is attributed to other factors not captured in the model for the period under review. The F – statistics of 18.96379, with a p-value of 0.000106 denotes that the influence of RGDP, EXCR, INF, and DTO on FDI is statistically significant.

4.5 Residual Diagnostic Result

Several diagnostic procedures were carried out to ensure the robustness of the estimates. These include the test for autocorrelation test, the heteroskedasticity test and the normality test. Table 6 below depicts the findings from the diagnostic tests.

Table 6: Diagnostic Test Results

Test	Statistics	P-value
Serial Correlation	1.072731	0.5849
Heteroskedasticity	11.71508	0.8974
Normality	0.710383	0.701039

Source: Author’s computation 2022 based on E-views

Table 6 above shows that the error terms in the short-run models are normally distributed, unaffected by heteroscedasticity, and devoid of serial correlation.

4.6 Stability Test

To check the stability of the long-run coefficients along with the short-run dynamics in the model, the cumulative sum (CUSUM) is employed. A graphical illustration of the CUSUM is shown below.

Fig 2: Cumulative Sum (CUSUM)

Source: Author’s computation 2022 based on E-views

The figure above reveals the cumulative sum (CUSUM) tests, which suggest no structural instability in the residuals of the model, which symbolizes the dynamics of FDI regarding RGDP, EXCR, INF and DTO. Furthermore, it can be seen that the plot of the CUSUM statistics fluctuates within the 5% critical bounds. Consequently, the estimated coefficients are stable for the period of study i.e. 1980 to 2020

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

This study evaluated the determinants of foreign direct investment in Nigeria from 1980 - 2020 utilizing the ARDL bounds testing approach. The result reveals the presence of a long-run relationship between foreign direct investment, real gross domestic product, exchange rate, inflation and degree of trade openness. The coefficient of real gross domestic product is positive and statistically significant both in the short and long run, meaning that an increase in the real gross domestic product increases foreign direct investment irrespective of the period. The exchange rate and degree of trade openness were positive and statistically significant in the long run, while the inflation rate was negative and statistically significant in the long run. The findings from this study give economic policymakers a better understanding of the importance of attracting foreign direct investment into Nigeria. The inflow of foreign direct investment into the Nigerian economy will allow the transfer of technology; contribute to the corporate tax revenue; create jobs; boost foreign exchange reserves; facilitate local and international trade; trigger innovation and productivity as well as drive economic growth. Based on these, it was recommended that: Government should create a conducive economic atmosphere for businesses to thrive; provide the necessary infrastructure and amenities to increase economic growth; reduce the level of insecurity in Nigeria; adopt policies to ensure stable exchange rates; implement uniform tax policies in accordance with global best practices; adopt an economic policy of privatization, liberalization and globalization to enhance trade openness with the rest of the world.

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